

Rethinking Gender Categorizations: Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard* as Postmodernist Intervention

Aseneh Nadesh Anjoh ✉
Department of English, The University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Article History:

Received: 02.07.2025 Revised: 19.07.2025 Accepted: 30.07.2025 Published: 07.08.2025

Abstract

In the century following modernism's peak, the literary landscape has witnessed a proliferation of gender categories, prompting a reevaluation of traditional binaries. Gender categorization, seems to occupy center stage in today's discussions. While interrogating existing categories of man/woman, he/she, it has been argued that gender is a spectrum – a continuous sequence. This therefore means that individuals are always or constantly seeking to define themselves through verbal expressions and actions. This paper revisits Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard* (2005) as a postmodernist text that employs narrative techniques to interrogate the rigidity of existing gender binaries within a described context. Through a queer and gender theory-infused analysis, the paper focuses on the protagonist - Emade's process of self-discovery, which is marked by experiences of paranoia and social marginalization. The paper contends that Epie's text uses the device or trope of the "bearded lady" as a means to parody and caricature "traditional" notions of gender. Emade's embodiment of this ambiguous, liminal figure serves to destabilize essentialist conceptions of masculinity and femininity. Through a close reading of the novel's narrative structure and characterization, the paper explores how *The Lady with a Beard* resists simplistic gender categorizations. It investigates the ways in which the text questions and subverts the very notion of gender as a stable, coherent identity. In doing so, the paper interrogates the role of social and historical context in shaping diverse expressions and experiences of gender. By positioning Epie's novel within the broader trajectory of post-modernist literature, this analysis contributes to scholarly discussions on the literary representation of gender nonconformity and the power of narrative to challenge normative frameworks. The paper offers insights into how the novel's formal and thematic strategies expand our understanding of gender today as a fluid, performative construct.

Keywords: *Queer, Gender, Parody.*

Suggested citation: Anjoh, A.N. (2025). Rethinking Gender Categorizations: Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard* as Postmodernist Intervention. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(4), 66-73. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(4\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(4).08)

Introduction

The evolution of philosophical and cultural paradigms has marked the progression of human thought and interpretation of the world. The transition from modernism to postmodernism (postmodernism which emerged as a critical response to the perceived limitations and

exclusions of modernism-) has given rise to a more fluid and deconstructed understanding of societal constructs, particularly those relating to gender and sexuality. This evolution has led us from accepting "traditional" narratives to inventing new frameworks, and ultimately to deconstructing and questioning established norms - a state that characterizes our present

condition. Notably, the realm of gender and sexuality has become increasingly fluid, a byproduct of modernist and postmodern thinking. In this context, gender discourses have undergone an epistemological shift, as prominent theorists sought to challenge the grand narratives of the past and envision new ways of conceptualizing sexual and gender identities. Influential thinkers, from Foucault (2013) to Butler (1990), Sedgwick, and Munoz (2009), have contributed to this intellectual shift. Their work has traced the mutation of the very meaning of gender - from its regulation by structures of power, to the separation of sex from the body, and the subsequent disentangling of gender from genitalia, culminating in a more neutral, fluid understanding of gender identity. Inevitably, postmodernist writers have engaged with this evolving dialogue on gender representation and mutation.

However, within the African cultural context, these new perspectives on gender and sexuality may be perceived as a rather "queer" inventions, diverging from the deeply sexed and heteronormative nature of the societal structures. It is from this vantage point that Alobwed'Epie's novel *The Lady with a Beard* can be seen as an attempt to mimics the isms inventions of gender. *The Lady with a Beard*, can be situated as a postmodernist intervention that engages with the mutation and representation of gender identities. Operating within a cultural context that is inherently sexed and heteronormative, the protagonist's journey of self-discovery, marked by disruption and liminality, disrupts the strict structures that seek to contain and codify gender expression.

This paper explores how Epie's narrative strategies in *The Lady with a Beard* engage with and challenge the prevailing gender norms within the African literary landscape. By situating the novel within the broader theoretical discourse on queer, gender and sexuality (sexuality as the total expression of self), this analysis seeks to illuminate the ways in which Epie as a contemporary African writer, grapples with the reevaluation of traditional norms in the wake of the post-modernist era. Through a critical engagement with the text's use of parody, caricature, and narrative strategies, the paper

contributes to ongoing scholarly conversations on the literary representation of gender nonconformity and the transformative potential of the postmodernist aesthetic.

This study undertakes an in-depth examination of the protagonist's struggle to define her sense of self within a cultural context that is perceived as regressive and dysfunctional. Marked by experiences of profound paranoia (an instinct or thought process, heavily influenced by anxiety, suspicion, fear often to the point of delusion and irrationality), the protagonist's journey of self-discovery becomes a site of contestation, where the normative boundaries of gender and identity are called into question. And argues that despite the nuanced incorporation of postmodernist tropes and theoretical frameworks, the Afro-postmodernist writer, has strategically transposed these inventions in a manner that problematizes the prevailing ideologies and endeavors within the cultural milieu. Through this sarcastic transposition, the text disrupts the rigid binary distinctions between men and women that have been deeply ingrained within the social fabric, challenging the very foundations upon which the gender status quo has been constructed and maintained.

Theory and Contextualization

The term "queer" in this context carries a multifaceted and expansive meaning, not limited to simply denoting sexual deviance. As David Halperin (2000) eloquently articulates, queer "demarcates not a positivity but a positionality vis-à-vis the normative" (p.5). It is an identity without a fixed essence, a site of permanent becoming. Furthermore, the concept of queer, as elaborated by Noreen Giffney, can be understood as an "umbrella term for those not only deemed sexually deviant, but also used to describe those who feel marginalized as a result of standard social practices" (p.7). Queer, then, becomes a positionality that challenges and resists the normative. Building upon the insights of Annamarie Jagose, (1999) this analysis acknowledges that queer is fundamentally a "mismatch between gender, sex, and desire" (p.1). It is this very mismatch that is manifested in the character of Emade, whose gender identity

and expression defy the binary constructions of masculinity and femininity.

By framing Emade and the text through a queer and Gender theoretical lens, this examination aims to illuminate the ways in which the narrative subverts and challenges the hegemonic gender norms and social practices that are deeply embedded within this cultural fabric of the Bakossi land. Through this analytical approach, new avenues for understanding the complexities of identity, desire, and marginalization are opened up for the discerning reader. The temporal and spatial setting of the Bakossi cultural context is discussed as imbued with a normative quality. However, the character of Emade is portrayed as diverging from and destabilizing this established heteronormativity. This tension between Emade's positionality and the dominant cultural constructs of "right" and "wrong" is a central thematic thrust within the narrative. Furthermore, the text employs the strategic use of foreshadowing, often manifested through the deployment of proverbs, to announce the underlying cultural worldview.

Queering Emade and the Text: A Subversive Reading

The analysis here, establish Emade as a non-binary character, and in doing so, posit that Emade and the literary text can and should be read through a queer theoretical lens. The analysis also delves into the ways in which Emade subverts the masculine-centric attributes and cultural imperatives that are deeply ingrained within her society. The author's strategic use of tone and gestural cues is examined to demonstrate how these narrative techniques create a sense of comic relief, while simultaneously heightening the dramatic tension inherent in the text. Crucially, the analysis posits that gender and gender identity within this literary work are presented as performative in nature. Emade's assumption of a new gender identity, "the lady with the beard," is read as a metonymic configuration that challenges the hegemonic constructions of masculinity that are pervasive within the contextual parameters of the novel.

The character Emade is developed in a manner that underscores her performance of culturally ascribed masculine roles, which paradoxically do not directly empower her or facilitate her own self-actualization. In the course of Emade's journey to design a new, alternative gender identity for herself, she strays far from the traditional female sphere, yet she also fails to fully embody a masculine identity. This liminal and conflicted position she occupies becomes the central unresolved puzzle that the novel leaves for the reader to grapple with. In her analysis, Mary Louisa (2011) presents a compelling argument in: "Non-conformist Heroine: The Assertive Female in Alowed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard*," suggesting that the narrative serves as a counter-discourse that highlights- the authority which African women Possess – In making her own choices amidst plenty proliferation of African Women as “oppressed and subjugated girl, wife or widow who can do very little in changing or shaping the system that deprives and oppresses her” (p.2), this perspective is somewhat limited.

While Emade does engage with culturally ascribed masculine roles, her journey reveals a complex tension: she neither fully embraces a traditional masculine identity nor finds empowerment within the confines of her existing identity as a woman. Instead, she occupies a liminal space that reflects her struggle for self-actualization, I argue that, despite the potential for empowerment, Emade's actions are often constrained by her paranoia, which inhibits her from pursuing more liberating choices. While Louisa emphasizes the authority of women in making choices, I believe that Emade's narrative illustrates the difficulties of enacting those choices when faced with deep-seated societal pressures and internal conflicts. There are more empowering paths available to her that remain unexplored, suggesting that the struggle for agency is more nuanced than Louisa acknowledges.

Throughout the narrative, Emade is portrayed as a steadfast custodian of her cultural heritage, exhibiting a deep and comprehensive understanding of its every aspect, which she enacts with precision. However, a crucial moment of rupture occurs when Emade sustains

an injury, and for the first time, she finds herself unable to comprehend the cultural significance of this occurrence. Notably, Emade's subsequent two-and-a-half-year-long quest for answers, as she repeatedly questions whether she was right or wrong in sending Ntube to the mission, marks a significant shift in the novel's thematic focus. The central question evolves from what Emade believes to be right, to a more nuanced interrogation of right and wrong from a communal, collective perspective.

The character of Emade is consistently portrayed as craving solitude and experiencing a form of isolation, both voluntary and involuntary, from the prevailing social structures within the narrative. This sense of being at odds with her surrounding society serves as a significant marker in the queering of Emade's identity and stand. The very first instance that establishes Emade as a queer character is her self-imposed abstraction from the social fabric, manifested in her decision to reside alone at the entrance of her community following the death of her husband. This act of seclusion can be read as a response to the feeling of non-belonging that often characterizes queer experiences.

I remember very well when Nye Emade's husband died some twelve years ago. Ntube was just four months old. the chief and councilors of this village wanted to move her to the center for two reasons 1) they said it was inappropriate for a widow with a baby to isolate from the rest of the village 2) that in a village where men incarnated Muanakum, a woman could not occupy the first compound - the entrance of the village. All the girls born and married here know that it was in the grove behind her late husband's house that Muanakum was incarnated for the building of the hammock. she categorically refused to move " (p.17-16)

This passage presents a critical juncture in the narrative that allows for a distinct exploration of queerness and gender within the cultural context of the Bakossi society. The central event described- the death of Emade's husband and the subsequent attempts by the community elders to displace her from her home.

Queer individuals, who often feel marginalized and misunderstood by the dominant social norms, frequently resort to self-imposed

isolation as a means of carving out a receptive world of their own. This withdrawal from the normative social structures allows for the creation of alternative spaces of belonging and self-expression. Emade's decision to live apart from her community can therefore be interpreted as a strategic act of queering, a rejection of the heteronormative expectations imposed upon her. Firstly, the insistence by the chief and councillors that it is "inappropriate" for a widowed woman with a young child to isolate herself from the rest of the village points to the deep-rooted patriarchal structures that seek to regulate female behavior and mobility emphasized by the word "widowed". The notion of appropriateness or "proper" feminine conduct is firmly embedded within the social fabric, rendering Emade's desire for solitude and self-determination as a transgressive act. However, Emade's steadfast refusal to be relocated outlines her unwillingness to submit to these cultural expectations. Her defiance of the community's demands signals a rejection of the heteronormative framework that seeks to confine her within the bounds of acceptable womanhood. By asserting her "right" to occupy the space at the entrance of the village, Emade's actions can be read as a reclamation of her own agency.

Furthermore, the passage highlights the cultural significance of the "hammock" and its association with the male deity, Muanakum. The text informs us that it is the grove behind Emade's late husband's house where this deity is incarnated, which is deemed an inappropriate space for a woman to occupy. This gendered spatial demarcation reinforces the patriarchal order, where certain domains are exclusively reserved for men and their sacred rituals. Emade's refusal to vacate this space, despite the community's attempts to enforce these gender-based boundaries, can be interpreted as a subversive act of queering. By asserting her presence in a realm deemed strictly masculine, Emade disrupts the normative gender hierarchies and challenges the very foundations of the Bakossi sociocultural system. "In Narrative Discourse and the Emergence of the New Rural woman in Alowed' Epie's *The Lady with a Beard* Ophelia Abianji Menang (2020)

tends to overgeneralize this specific event or situation in her analysis, particularly regarding the appropriateness of Emade's presence at the village entrance. It remains uncertain whether her gender or her status as a widow significantly influences the elders' decision. Menang interprets this incident as emblematic of the text's broader theme, which she claims centers on "raising awareness of the predicaments of widows in Cameroonian society." (p.1) However, this interpretation overlooks the complexity of Emade's situation. While she faces reprimands and restrictions from assuming certain male-oriented roles, these limitations cannot be solely attributed to her status as a widow. Instead, they reflect a more nuanced interplay between gender, societal expectations, and individual identity.

Emade's fervent desire for solitude and isolation emerges as a prominent aspect of her characterization. In one notable instance, she goes so far as to hide her chairs, effectively preventing others from occupying her home. Furthermore, she is conspicuously estranged from the various women's groups and activities within her community. While some of these actions may appear peculiar, they collectively contribute to the queering of Emade's identity. What makes Emade's character particularly subversive is her apparent satisfaction with this self-imposed distance. Rather than viewing it as a burden, she seems to embrace it as a means of creating a space of her own – a sanctuary where she can assert her autonomy and individuality. This resilience and inner strength, the courageous soul that Mademoiselle Reisz in *The Awakening* announces that all subversive characters must possess, further underscores Emade's non-conformist disposition. In contrast to Munge's own sense of emptiness, she, describes Emade as no ordinary woman a testament to her unwavering spirit and refusal to be defined by societal expectations. "Nye Emade is not an empty woman she is full to the brim. As I am here before you, I am as empty as a broken jar. She who wants to fight a tiger, must have claws and fangs" (p.7). The text's sustained focus on Emade's spatial and social isolation, as well as her resolute defiance of communal norms, illuminates the subversive potential of

Emade's embodiment of otherness, which disrupts the hegemonic structures and opens up new possibilities for reimagining the boundaries of gender and belonging.

Emade's character can be viewed through the lens of Jose Esteban Munoz's (2009) conceptualization of queerness *Cruising Utopia, the then and Now of Queer Futurity*, as a "feeling that lets us feel that the world is not enough indeed, something is missing, often we glimpse the world proposed and promised by queer in the realms of the aesthetics" (p.1). Emade's interactions with her heteronormative society reveal a profound sense of dissatisfaction with the rigid gender norms and expectations imposed upon her and a vision of a more utopian reality Munoz's assertion that queerness exists in the "realms of the aesthetic" resonates strongly with Emade's own subversive embodiment of gender. Emade's unwillingness to conform to the prescribed feminine ideals of her community, such as her refusal to occupy the "appropriate" spaces designated for women, can be read as a rejection of the culturally inscribed "mental categories" that seek to restrict her identity. Emade's inward recognition that the world as it is presented to her is "not enough" drives her to actively invert the gender roles and challenge the heteronormative status quo. Her ability to perfectly execute these subversive performances, to the admiration of her community, further underscores the constructed nature of gender and the potential for alternative expressions of identity.

Emade's quest for a world where the aesthetic reproduction of cultural practices is not restricted to a particular person hints at her desire for a more fluid and inclusive understanding of gender and cultural belonging. To her, the essence is for accomplishment and a fulfilment of purpose. Her probing questions "if a woman digs a grave does she remain in it? if a wake is not fully attended, does the corpse refuse to be buried? if a woman lays a corpse in the grave, does it jump out?" (43) serve to interrogate the gendered assumptions that undergird specific cultural practices, inviting the reader to re-examine the foundations of these norms. In this sense, Emade's character can be seen as a representation of Noreen Giffney's

conceptualization of queerness as a "site of permanent becoming" – a space where "marginalized" identities can continually reimagine and renegotiate their place within the social fabric. Emade's rejection and obliteration of the gendered restrictions imposed upon her echoes the broader project of queer theory and post-modernist thinking, which seeks to unsettle the normative structures and expand the possibilities for self-determination.

In the queer-themed text, the protagonist Emade is often portrayed as grappling with a deep sense of anxiety and unease about her place within the rigid societal norms. The narrative mechanics and thematic elements of the work suggest a story about the arduous attempt to "pass" as normal and perform the culturally prescribed masculine gender roles, all the while living with the ever-present risk of being ostracized as a non-normative individual. Beneath the ostensibly "feminist" veneer of the text, as has been read by most scholars (like Derick Mbungang in "Male Chauvenism and Female Resistance in Alowed Epié's *The Lady with the Beard*" there are abundant queer metaphors and symbols that subtly undermine the heteronormative status quo. Emade is metaphorically described as "knobby firewood" and a "mud fish,". Her sister ponders "I wonder why they are treating you like Knobby firewood - splitting and turning its sides (26), alluding to Emade's stubborn refusal to simply conform to what is generally accepted as the norm. Emade's internal struggle is vividly manifested when she agonizes over the decision to send her daughter Ntube to the mission, a choice that causes her a great deal of unease and prompts her to seek validation for her actions. The instance of Emade injuring her "foot of bad omen," which she then proceeds to invert, represents the complex and often contradictory nature of the non-conformist or queer psyche. This doubleness, where the outward self seeks to appease societal expectations while the inward self constantly questions the imposed norms, is a central aspect of Emade's character. However, the text suggests that Emade has already transcended the stage of mere inward questioning, as she actively searches for answers to resolve her internal conflicts and navigate the

heteronormative landscape. Through this nuanced portrayal of Emade's struggle, the text invites the reader to engage with the multifaceted dimensions of queer identity and the profound sense of disquiet that often accompanies the refusal to conform to societal dictates.

The text is marked by a profound tension between the forces demanding submission and those that attempt to assert full personhood. This manifests as a collision between Emade's burgeoning masculinity and the societal imposition of compulsory femininity. There are numerous indicators that Emade's behavior and identity do not align with the prescribed social norms for her gender, leaving both men and women in a state of constant awe and uncertainty. Consequently, there are ongoing debates about how to discipline and punish Emade in a way that does not equate her to a man. In a reiteration of her fluid, unclassifiable nature, Emade is described as "unpredictable as the rainy season weather" (P.40). As a result, both men and women devise strategies to discipline her, but find them difficult to implement due to the adverse effects such measures would have on the maintenance of societal norms – and the true function of any form of punishment is the retention of power. (Foucault 121). When the men realize that they cannot discipline Emade in the ways they desire, they are forced to devise alternative means, as granting her the appropriate form of punishment would represent a decentralization of masculine power.

That woman is our guest, if we incarnate Muankum against her she has no but here in front of which Muankum will defecate. Muankum will go and defecate at the border between our two villages for her to clean the faeces. since women don't settle cases on the border between two villages, the case will move from her to her village... suppose her village accepts to clean the faeces by offering a cow, she would be the one to provide the cow. Her chief will simply provide the cow at the border. she will be the one to eat the head of the cow. suppose tomorrow she says she was initiated in the cult of settling boarder dispute, will she be right or not. you see, some problems are like porcupines. no matter how right you are, you don't grip them with bare hands. (50)

This complex dynamic speaks to the text's profound engagement with the contestation of gender norms and the strategies employed to uphold the existing power structures. Emade's very presence and refusal to conform challenges the normative assumptions, compelling the dominant forces to grapple with the subversive potential of non-conformity.

This passage highlights the complex power dynamics at play within the social and cultural context depicted in the text. The proposed "punishment" of Emade, through the invocation of the Muankum ritual represents a clear attempt by the male authority figures to reassert their dominance and retain the existing power structures. Foucault's analysis of punishment as a means of power retention is highly relevant here. As he argues, the true function of punishment is not solely about correcting individual behavior, but rather about maintaining the broader system of power relations within a society. By subjecting Emade to a humiliating and ostracizing ritual, the community leaders are seeking to reinforce the social hierarchies that place women in a subordinate position.

The passage demonstrates how the men strategize to discipline Emade in a way that does not directly equate her to a man, as that would challenge the gender norms they are seeking to uphold. Instead, they devise a punishment that exploits the gendered dynamics of the community, where women are expected to clean up the "feaces" and provide the requisite sacrificial offering. The narrative's exploration of these themes underscores the transformative possibilities inherent in the assertion of fluid, non-binary identities, and the ways in which they disrupt the rigid gender binaries that undergird societal organization and power relations.

Conclusion

The analysis in this paper illustrates how Epie's text challenges the notion of gender as a stable and coherent identity and contends that Epie's text uses the device or trope of the "bearded lady" as a means to parody and caricature "traditional" notions of gender. It equally situates this work within the broader framework of postmodern literature, through the lens of

queer and gender theory the study reveals significant insights into the complexities of gender identity in a postmodern context. This examination underscores the pressing need to move beyond rigid binaries that defined specific roles of man and woman, he and she, recognizing the fluidity and performative nature of gender as a spectrum. Epie's employment of the "bearded lady" trope not only subverts traditional gender norms but also serves as a powerful critique of societal expectations surrounding masculinity and femininity. The protagonist, Emade, embodies a journey of self-discovery that is fraught with paranoia and social marginalization, thereby highlighting the often-painful realities faced by those who defy conventional gender categorizations. Through a careful examination of the narrative structure and characterization, we gained a deeper understanding of how narrative strategies can be employed to disrupt normative frameworks and enrich discussions on gender nonconformity. Ultimately, this study challenges us to embrace the complexities and ambiguities of identity and to recognize diverse gender expressions.

References

- Butler, J. (1990). *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. London, United Kingdom: Routledge. (ISBN: 0-415-38955-0)
- Charles, A. E. (2005). *The Lady with a Beard*. Yaoundé, Cameroon: Editions CLÉ. (ISBN: 995609028X / 9789956090280)
- Chopin, K. (1899). *The Awakening*. Louisiana, USA: Louisiana Press.
- Foucault, M. (2013). *The History of Sexuality*. Edinburgh, Scotland: Edinburgh University Press.
- Halperin, D. (2000). *The Normalization of Queer*. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.
- Jagose, A.-M. (1999). *Queer Theory: An Introduction*. London, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.

Lum, M. L. (2011). Non-conformist heroine: The assertive female in Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard*. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, 1–5.

Mbungang, D. (2019). Male chauvinism and female resistance in Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard*. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 3(2), 1–12.

Menang, O. A. (2020). Narrative discourse and the emergence of the new rural woman in Alobwed'Epie's *The Lady with a Beard*. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 7(6), 249–257.

Munoz, J. E. (2009). *Cruising Utopia: The Then and Now of Queer Theory*. New York, NY: New York University Press.